

METHODS OF MEASURING HYDROTECHNICAL STRUCTURES USING DIGITAL GEODESIC TECHNOLOGIES

Suyunova Hilola Nizam kizi

PhD student of Samarkand architecture-construction university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14547394>

Abstract: This article examines the use of digital geodetic technologies, their advantages and efficiency in the measurement of hydrotechnical structures. The importance of high-precision measurement systems in monitoring the safety and functional condition of hydraulic facilities is highlighted. As a result of the use of digital technologies, significant simplicity and accuracy are provided in the monitoring and analysis of structures.

Keywords: *digital geodetic technologies, hydrotechnical structures, monitoring, measurement methods, drones, 3D scanning, satellite images.*

Introduction. Hydrotechnical structures (dams, reservoirs, canals and other objects) play an important role in the management of society's water resources and ensuring safety. Controlling the strength and performance of these structures requires accurate measurement data.[1] Digital geodetic technologies are modern methods that can be used to automate and optimize measurement and monitoring processes.

Providing geodetic construction is a combination of engineering work and topographic research in the construction of structures and other infrastructure. Cooperation is carried out through a special geodetic service consisting of specialists in this field from the beginning to the end of the work. Today, receiving information from the land through the electronic information system does not meet the demand. A modern and rapid way of conducting land monitoring is the analysis of places with the help of GAT programs. The advantage of newly created electronic and digital maps is that correcting some errors made during the process of creating the map does not cause any problems and does not require a lot of time.[2]

The main part. Hydrotechnical structures are structures built for the use of water resources or to combat the effects of water erosion. Digital geodetic technologies are systems that integrate traditional geodetic methods with modern digital tools. They include the following technologies:

- GPS/GNSS systems: determining the coordinates of objects with high accuracy.
- 3D laser scanning: creating three-dimensional models of structures.
- Using drones: making quick measurements in complex and large areas.
- Satellite imagery: observation and analysis of large areas.

The methods of measuring hydrotechnical structures are as follows:

1. Measurement using GPS/GNSS

- Application: Determining the coordinates of objects such as dams, reservoirs and canals.
- Advantages: High accuracy, real-time measurement capability, coverage of wide areas.
- Example: Determining deformations along the perimeter of the reservoir using the GPS system.

2. 3D laser scanning technology

- Application: Determining the geometry of structures, analyzing deformations and creating 3D models.
- Advantages: Accuracy and detailed results, creating a realistic view of objects.
- Example: Creating a 3D model to identify cracks and irregularities of a dam.

3. Use of drones

- Application: Obtaining high-resolution images of large areas and complex objects.
- Advantages: Monitoring of hard-to-reach areas, fast and cost-effective.
- Example: Measurement of level heights along the canal and determination of soil erosion.

4. Satellite images

- Application: Monitoring of large areas, monitoring of movement and changes of water resources.
- Advantages: continuous monitoring of the area, long-term analysis.
- Example: Analysis of water level changes in reservoirs.

5. Network monitoring systems

- Application: Real-time monitoring of the structural condition of the building using sensors.
- Advantages: Timely warning system and increased security.
- Example: Measuring the deformation of a dam using sensors.[3]

Practical results and efficiency:

-High-precision digital technologies allow regular monitoring of the condition of hydrotechnical structures.

- The use of digital geodetic technologies helps to extend the service life of structures and ensure safety.

- Costs of monitoring processes are reduced due to quick and economic efficiency.

Summary. The use of digital geodetic technologies creates new opportunities in the measurement and monitoring of hydrotechnical structures. These technologies provide high accuracy and speed, while increasing the safety of facilities. In the future, it is desirable to introduce digital technologies more widely and expand their capabilities. this applies to all types of construction - residential and public buildings, road and transport networks, hydrotechnical structures, urban infrastructure.[4] Most issues are solved using information modeling technology. BIM helps control time, reduce construction costs, and reduce risks. BIM technology is not a software product, but a process.

Hydrotechnical structures are the most complex objects of water infrastructure in construction, taking into account geographical, economic, infrastructural, ecological and technological aspects. World technologies and management standards allow not only to take into account these factors, but also to manage a large amount of information about hydraulic facilities directly during the design process and at the next stages of the construction. This not only simplifies the work, but also saves the client's time and money.

References:

1. www.ziyonet.uz.
2. Karabekov U.A. APPLICATION OF GEOSPATIC TECHNOLOGIES FOR GEODESIC SURVEYING OF BUILDINGS // *Ekonomika i sotsium*. 2024. #5-2 (120). URL: https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/applying_geospacial-technologies-to-provide_geodetic_facilities (data obrashcheniya: 27.11.2024).
3. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hydrotechnika_inshutlari
4. Arifdjan Maksudovich Khodjayev, Umida Akhmadjanovna Nasritdinova, Zilola Maksudovna Gaibnazarova APPLICATION OF MODERN MODELING TECHNOLOGIES IN DESIGNING HYDROTECHNICAL CONSTRUCTIONS // *Academic research in educational sciences*. 2021. #6. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/utilization-of-modern-modeling-technologies-in-hydrotechnological-structures-design> (data obrashcheniya: 27.11.2024).